

NETWORK FREQUENCY AND COSINE SIMILARITY MEASURE

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Abstract

The Pythagorean fuzzy set is extended from intuitionistic fuzzy set. Pythagorean fuzzy sets are characterized by the three degrees such that membership, non-membership, and hesitancy which satisfies the condition that the sum of the squares of its membership degree, and non-membership degree is equal to or less than one. It reaches many application with the support of score, Accuracy, Distance, and Similarity measures. In this paper, the Pythagorean fuzzy set is explained with the help of cosine similarity and distance-based similarity. An illustrative example is also included and a comparative study is made with the Score, Accuracy, and Similarity measure function.

Key words

Pythagorean fuzzy set Cosine Similarity Measure Similarity Measure using Distance
function Score function Accuracy function

Mathematics Subject Classifications (2010) : 94D05.

1 Introduction

The theory of fuzzy sets, which has been used in many fields [4-7,14,22]. Atanassov [2] initiated the concept of an intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) in which he considered both the membership and non-membership functions. After that Yager [32] introduced the Pythagorean fuzzy set (PFS) as an efficient expansion of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets, whose sum of squares is less than or equal to one. A Pythagorean fuzzy set is also extended into different forms, such as interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy set [5], decision making [8,33,34], hesitant Pythagorean fuzzy set [9,15], and linguistic Pythagorean fuzzy set [10], and some other applications [35].

For determining the degree of similarity between two objects, the similarity measures are important. The similarity measure is a significant means for measuring uncertain information. Distance and similarity measure are two important topics in the fuzzy set theory and have extensively been applied in some fields such as decision making, Pattern recognition, machine learning, market prediction, and so on. Wang [27] proposed two new similarity measures between fuzzy sets and elements. Szmidt and Kacprzyk [25] gave a new distance measure between two intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Narukawa and Torra [17] introduced a weighted distance measure for intuitionistic fuzzy sets based on the Choquet integral concerning the non-monotonic fuzzy measure.

Bernadette Bouchon [3] introduced the concept of the real-world application of fuzzy techniques for information retrieval and data mining. Fuzzy logic is very useful in soft approaches of man-machine interaction and online or offline learning of the best way to satisfy the demand because of its capability to represent miscellaneous data in a synthetic way, its robustness with regard to changes of the parameters of the user's environment, obviously its unique expressiveness. Fuzzy sets, Bipolar fuzzy sets, Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, and bipolar intuitionistic fuzzy sets [28] proposed that they can deal with dubious data all the more flexibly during the process of decision making.

Shi and Olson [18] introduced the fundamentals of data mining and Shi [23] explained the advances of Big data analytics which describes and demonstrate basic data mining algorithm and various techniques for solving big data problems. Optimization techniques [24] were widely adopted to implement various data mining algorithms in data separations. It mainly focused on multiple criteria programming and support vector machines and real-life applications in various fields like web services, bio-informatics, and petroleum engineering. Tien [26] introduced real-time decision making in the internet of things which includes its improving abilities at voice and video recognition, speech and predictive synthesis, language, and social media understanding.

Zeng and Li [38] investigated the relationship between the inclusion measure, the similarity measure, and the fuzziness of fuzzy sets. Peng and Yang [21] developed a Pythagorean fuzzy superiority and inferiority ranking method to solve uncertainty multiple attribute group decision-making problems. Zhang [37] proposed Pythagorean fuzzy similarity measures in the multi-attribute decision-making problems. Peng [20] proposed the many new distance measures and similarity measures for dealing with many issues such as pattern recognition, medical diagnosis, and clustering analysis. Wei and Wei [29] presented some Pythagorean fuzzy cosine similarities for the decision-making problems.

In this paper, In order to find out the degree of similarity between Pythagorean fuzzy sets, the extended form of the cosine similarity measure is recommended. A numerical example is illustrated to demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed extended cosine similarity measure.

This paper is organized as follows: In section 2, some basic concepts are briefly introduced. An algorithm is proposed in section 3. In section 4, an example is illustrated for the proposed algorithm and section 5 reveals the result and discussion. Finally, conclusion is delivered in section 6.

2 Concepts

In this section some concepts, related to Pythagorean fuzzy sets are introduced.

Definition 2.1

Let X be a fixed set, then a fuzzy sets A in X can be defined as

$$A = \{ x, \alpha_A(x) / x \in X \}$$

where $\alpha_A : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is called membership degree of $x \in X$.

Definition 2.2

Let X be a fixed set, then the Intuitionistic fuzzy set in X can be defined as:

$$I = \{ x, \alpha_I(x), \beta_I(x) / x \in X \}$$

Where $\alpha_I(x)$ and $\beta_I(x)$ are mapping from X to $[0,1]$ with condition $0 \leq \alpha_I(x) \leq 1, 0 \leq \beta_I(x) \leq 1, 0 \leq \alpha_I(x) + \beta_I(x) \leq 1$ for all $x \in X$. Let $\nu_I(x) = 1 - \alpha_I(x) - \beta_I(x)$ then it is called the intuitionistic fuzzy index of $x \in X$ to the set I , representing the degree of indeterminacy x to I . Also $0 \leq \nu_I(x) \leq 1$ for every $x \in X$.

Definition 2.3

Let X be a fixed set, then Pythagorean fuzzy set in X can be defined as follows:

$$P(X) = \{ x, \alpha_p(x), \beta_p(x) / x \in X \}$$

Where $\alpha_p(x)$ and $\beta_p(x)$ are mapping from X to $[0,1]$ with condition $0 \leq \alpha_p(x) \leq 1, 0 \leq \beta_p(x) \leq 1$, also $0 \leq \alpha_p^2(x) + \beta_p^2(x) \leq 1$ for all $x \in X$ and they denote the degree of membership and degree of non membership of element $x \in X$ to the set P respectively.

Definition 2.4

Let X and Y be 2 pythagorean fuzzy sets $X, Y \in P(X)$ then the operations can be defined as follows:

- i) $X \cup Y = \{ \langle x, \max(\alpha_X(x), \alpha_Y(x)), \min(\beta_X(x), \beta_Y(x)) \rangle | x \in X \}$
- ii) $X \cap Y = \{ \langle x, \min(\alpha_X(x), \alpha_Y(x)), \max(\beta_X(x), \beta_Y(x)) \rangle | x \in X \}$
- iii) $X + Y = \{ \langle x, \sqrt{\alpha_X^2(x) + \alpha_Y^2(x) - \alpha_X^2(x)\alpha_Y^2(x)}, \beta_X(x)\beta_Y(x) \rangle | x \in X \}$
- iv) $X \times Y = \{ \langle x, \alpha_X(x)\alpha_Y(x), \sqrt{\beta_X^2(x) + \beta_Y^2(x) - \beta_X^2(x)\beta_Y^2(x)} \rangle | x \in X \}$
- v) $X^c = \{ \langle x, \beta_X(x), \alpha_X(x) \rangle | x \in X \}$.

Definition 2.5

Let X be the Pythagorean fuzzy set $X, Y \in P(X)$ then the Score and Accuracy functions of X is defined as follows:

$$S_c(X) = \alpha_X^2(x) - \beta_X^2(x), \text{ Where } S_c(X) \in [-1, 1]$$

$$A_c(X) = \alpha_X^2(x) + \beta_X^2(x), \text{ Where } A_c(X) \in [0, 1].$$

For any 2 pythagorean fuzzy sets, X and Y is compared as follows:

- i) If $S_c(X) > S_c(Y)$ then $X > Y$
- ii) If $S_c(X) = S_c(Y)$ then
 - a) if $A_c(X) > A_c(Y)$ then $X > Y$
 - b) if $A_c(X) = A_c(Y)$ then $X \sim Y$.

Definition 2.6

Let X and Y be two pythagorean fuzzy sets $X, Y \in P(X)$. Then the similarity measures $S(X, Y)$ are defined as follows:

i) Cosine Similarity Measure:

$$S_1(X, Y) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\alpha_X^2(x_i)\alpha_Y^2(x_i) + \beta_X^2(x_i)\beta_Y^2(x_i)}{\sqrt{\alpha_X^4(x_i) + \beta_X^4(x_i)}\sqrt{\alpha_Y^4(x_i) + \beta_Y^4(x_i)}}$$

ii) Similarity Measure based on Hamming Distance:

$$S_2(X, Y) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (|\alpha_X^2(x_i) - \alpha_Y^2(x_i)| + |\beta_X^2(x_i) - \beta_Y^2(x_i)|)}{2n}$$

Definition 2.7

Let X, Y and Z be three pythagorean fuzzy sets on X . A similarity measure $S(X, Y)$ is a mapping $S: P(X) \times P(X) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ possessing the following properties.

- i) $0 \leq S(X, Y) \leq 1$
- ii) $S(X, Y) = S(Y, X)$
- iii) $S(X, Y) = 1$ iff $X = Y$
- iv) $S(X, X^c) = 0$ iff X is a crisp set.
- v) If $X \subseteq Y \subseteq Z$, then $S(X, Z) \leq S(X, Y)$ and $S(X, Z) \leq S(Y, Z)$.

3 Algorithm

This algorithm yields the network frequency path through path length from the source node to the destination node in a directed acyclic network with a Pythagorean fuzzy set.

Step 1: Initialization

Assign a Pythagorean fuzzy number for each arc between all pairs of nodes.

Step 2: Analyzation

Analyze the path length for all possible paths from the source node to the destination node in the network using the formula

$$X + Y = \{ \langle x, \sqrt{\alpha_X^2(x) + \alpha_Y^2(x) - \alpha_X^2(x)\alpha_Y^2(x)}, \beta_X(x)\beta_Y(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$$

Where X and Y are two pythagorean fuzzy numbers.

Step 3: Calculation

Calculate the minimum path length from all possible paths by the following formula

$$X \cap Y = \{ \langle x, \min(\alpha_X(x), \alpha_Y(x)), \max(\beta_X(x), \beta_Y(x)) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$$

Step 4: Computation

using cosine similarity Calculate the value of all possible paths with minimum path length.

$$S_1(X, Y) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\alpha_X^2(x_i)\alpha_Y^2(x_i) + \beta_X^2(x_i)\beta_Y^2(x_i)}{\sqrt{\alpha_X^4(x_i) + \beta_X^4(x_i)}\sqrt{\alpha_Y^4(x_i) + \beta_Y^4(x_i)}}$$

Step 5: Identification of Network Frequency Path

Network shortest frequency path is fixed with the shortest path which is having the highest similarity measure.

4 Numerical Example

In this section, a wide telecommunicated network is considered to illustrate the proposed method.

Consider a Zoom meeting, which is organized by one country (source) to another country (destination) through various countries (intermediate nodes), while we are

organizing the zoom meeting through the network there may be various paths available to connect from source to destination. The Pythagorean fuzzy number is assigned to the flow of frequency. The organizer wants to find the shortest frequency path in which we can get good result in sound clarity (x_1), video clarity (x_2), and minimum number of network traffic (x_3) in the given finite universe $X \{ x_1, x_2, x_3 \}$.

In these three, the organizer is focusing on the clarity (α_i) and the speed of the network (β_i).

Fig. 4.1 An example of PFS network

Solution:

Step 1:

Each arc length is assigned to Pythagorean fuzzy number.

$$1 - 2 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.4, 0.5 \rangle \langle x_2 0.3, 0.4 \rangle \langle x_3 0.1, 0.2 \rangle$$

$$1 - 3 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.1, 0.3 \rangle \langle x_2 0.5, 0.7 \rangle \langle x_3 0.3, 0.6 \rangle$$

$$1 - 4 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.2, 0.4 \rangle \langle x_2 0.4, 0.5 \rangle \langle x_3 0.6, 0.7 \rangle$$

$$1 - 5 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.3, 0.4 \rangle \langle x_2 0.1, 0.3 \rangle \langle x_3 0.5, 0.8 \rangle$$

$$2 - 6 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.2, 0.3 \rangle \langle x_2 0.4, 0.6 \rangle \langle x_3 0.4, 0.5 \rangle$$

$$3 - 6 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.4, 0.6 \rangle \langle x_2 0.2, 0.3 \rangle \langle x_3 0.4, 0.7 \rangle$$

$$3 - 7 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.4, 0.7 \rangle \langle x_2 0.5, 0.6 \rangle \langle x_3 0.3, 0.6 \rangle$$

$$3 - 9 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.6, 0.7 \rangle \langle x_2 0.1, 0.5 \rangle \langle x_3 0.6, 0.7 \rangle$$

$$4 - 7 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.6, 0.7 \rangle \langle x_2 0.3, 0.7 \rangle \langle x_3 0.6, 0.8 \rangle$$

$$5 - 7 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.5, 0.6 \rangle \langle x_2 0.2, 0.4 \rangle \langle x_3 0.3, 0.6 \rangle$$

$$6 - 8 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.3, 0.4 \rangle \langle x_2 0.5, 0.6 \rangle \langle x_3 0.4, 0.6 \rangle$$

$$6 - 9 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.3, 0.6 \rangle \langle x_2 0.4, 0.5 \rangle \langle x_3 0.6, 0.7 \rangle$$

$$7 - 9 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.5, 0.8 \rangle \langle x_2 0.3, 0.5 \rangle \langle x_3 0.1, 0.5 \rangle$$

$$7 - 11 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.2, 0.5 \rangle \langle x_2 0.5, 0.7 \rangle \langle x_3 0.3, 0.6 \rangle$$

$$7 - 12 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.3, 0.5 \rangle \langle x_2 0.2, 0.4 \rangle \langle x_3 0.4, 0.5 \rangle$$

$$8 - 10 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.4, 0.6 \rangle \langle x_2 0.3, 0.7 \rangle \langle x_3 0.4, 0.6 \rangle$$

$$9 - 10 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.2, 0.7 \rangle \langle x_2 0.1, 0.5 \rangle \langle x_3 0.3, 0.4 \rangle$$

$$9 - 12 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.3, 0.5 \rangle \langle x_2 0.6, 0.7 \rangle \langle x_3 0.4, 0.6 \rangle$$

$$10 - 12 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.1, 0.3 \rangle \langle x_2 0.5, 0.8 \rangle \langle x_3 0.2, 0.6 \rangle$$

$$11 - 12 \rightarrow \langle x_1 0.5, 0.6 \rangle \langle x_2 0.3, 0.6 \rangle \langle x_3 0.5, 0.7 \rangle$$

Step 2: Analyzation

There are 16 possible path lengths between source node to destination node.

The possible paths and its lengths are

$$P_1: 1-2-6-8-10-12 = \langle x_1 0.678, 0.11 \rangle \langle x_2 0.916, 0.081 \rangle \langle x_3 0.728, 0.022 \rangle$$

$$P_2: 1-2-6-9-10-12 = \langle x_1 0.583, 0.019 \rangle \langle x_2 0.819, 0.048 \rangle \langle x_3 0.812, 0.017 \rangle$$

$$P_3: 1-2-6-9-12 = \langle x_1 0.616, 0.045 \rangle \langle x_2 0.877, 0.084 \rangle \langle x_3 0.831, 0.042 \rangle$$

$$P_4: 1-3-6-8-10-12 = \langle x_1 0.656, 0.013 \rangle \langle x_2 0.938, 0.071 \rangle \langle x_3 0.781, 0.091 \rangle$$

$$P_5: 1-3-6-9-10-12 = \langle x_1 0.557, 0.023 \rangle \langle x_2 0.843, 0.042 \rangle \langle x_3 0.86, 0.017 \rangle$$

$$P_6: 1-3-6-9-12 = \langle x_1 0.592, 0.054 \rangle \langle x_2 0.899, 0.074 \rangle \langle x_3 0.877, 0.176 \rangle$$

$$P_7: 1-3-9-10-12 = \langle x_1 0.648, 0.044 \rangle \langle x_2 0.721, 0.14 \rangle \langle x_3 0.762, 0.101 \rangle$$

$$P_8: 1-3-9-12 = \langle x_1 0.678, 0.105 \rangle \langle x_2 0.787, 0.245 \rangle \langle x_3 0.778, 0.252 \rangle$$

$$P_9: 1-3-7-9-10-12 = \langle x_1 0.686, 0.035 \rangle \langle x_2 0.922, 0.084 \rangle \langle x_3 0.566, 0.043 \rangle$$

$$P_{10}: 1-3-7-9-12 = \langle x_1 0.714, 0.084 \rangle \langle x_2 0.974, 0.14 \rangle \langle x_3 0.592, 0.108 \rangle$$

$$P_{11}: 1-3-7-12 = \langle x_1 0.509, 0.105 \rangle \langle x_2 0.733, 0.168 \rangle \langle x_3 0.582, 0.18 \rangle$$

$$P_{12}: 1-3-7-11-12 = \langle x_1 0.678, 0.063 \rangle \langle x_2 0.916, 0.176 \rangle \langle x_3 0.721, 0.151 \rangle$$

$$P_{13}: 1-4-7-9-10-12 = \langle x_1 0.837, 0.047 \rangle \langle x_2 0.775, 0.07 \rangle \langle x_3 0.927, 0.067 \rangle$$

$$P_{14}: 1-4-7-9-12 = \langle x_1 0.86, 0.112 \rangle \langle x_2 0.836, 0.123 \rangle \langle x_3 0.943, 0.168 \rangle$$

$$P_{15}: 1-4-7-12 = \langle x_1 0.699, 0.14 \rangle \langle x_2 0.538, 0.14 \rangle \langle x_3 0.927, 0.28 \rangle$$

$$P_{16}: 1-4-7-11-12 = \langle x_1 0.831, 0.84 \rangle \langle x_2 0.768, 0.147 \rangle \langle x_3 1., 0.235 \rangle$$

Step 3: Calculation

Calculation of Minimum path length with all possible paths.

$$X \cap Y = \{ \langle x, \min(\alpha_X(x), \alpha_Y(x)), \max(\beta_X(x), \beta_Y(x)) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$$

$$P_{\min} = P_1 \cap P_2 = \{ \langle x_1, (\min(0.678, 0.583), \max(0.011, 0.019)), \langle x_2, \min(0.916, 0.819), (\max(0.081, 0.048)), \langle x_3, (\min(0.728, 0.812), \max(0.022, 0.017)) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$$

$$P_{\min} = P_1 \cap P_2 = \langle x_1 0.583, 0.19 \rangle \langle x_2 0.819, 0.081 \rangle \langle x_3 0.728, 0.022 \rangle$$

$$P_{\min} = P_{\min} \cap P_3 = \langle x_1 0.583, 0.19 \rangle \langle x_2 0.819, 0.084 \rangle \langle x_3 0.728, 0.042 \rangle$$

Similarly the comparison is made with all possible path lengths and finally minimum path length is calculated.

$$P_{\min} = \langle x_1 0.509, 0.14 \rangle \langle x_2 0.538, 0.176 \rangle \langle x_3 0.4, 0.28 \rangle$$

Step 4: Computation

Calculation of Cosine similarity measure for all possible path lengths with minimum path length.

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_1) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\alpha_X^2(x_i)\alpha_Y^2(x_i) + \beta_X^2(x_i)\beta_Y^2(x_i)}{\sqrt{\alpha_X^4(x_i) + \beta_X^4(x_i)}\sqrt{\alpha_Y^4(x_i) + \beta_Y^4(x_i)}}$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_1) = 0.9133$$

Similarly,

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_2) = 0.9147$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_3) = 0.91$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_4) = 0.9092$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_5) = 0.9143$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_6) = 0.9094$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_7) = 0.921$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_8) = 0.919$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_9) = 0.9148$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_{10}) = 0.914$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_{11}) = 0.923$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_{12}) = 0.914$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_{13}) = 0.909$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_{14}) = 0.907$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_{15}) = 0.9199$$

$$S_1(P_{min}, P_{16}) = 0.9073$$

Similarly, Similarity measure based on Hamming distance also calculated and compared with cosine similarity.

Step 5: Identification of Shortest Path

The highest similarity measure is $S_1(P_{min}, P_{11}) = 0.923$.

This similarity measure corresponds to the path 1-3-7-12, which is identified as Network shortest frequency path. This path is having more clarity and high speed.

5 Result and Discussion

The clarity and network speed from source node to destination node are found in the frequency $< x_1 0.509, 0.105 > < x_2 0.733, 0.168 > < x_3 0.582, 0.18 >$. In each arc sound clarity, video clarity, and network traffic is maintained throughout the path. Shortest frequency path between source node to the destination node with highest speed and clarity are calculated using a cosine similarity measure.

The results are tabulated and compared with Score, Accuracy, and Similarity measure based on Hamming distance also. Clear variations between the paths are obtained since the Pythagorean fuzzy number can accommodate multi attributes than any other fuzzy number.

S.No.	Possible Paths	$S_1(P_{min}, P_i)$	$S_2(P_{min}, P_i)$	Score Value	Accuracy	Rank
1.	P ₁ (1-2-6-8-10-12)	0.9133	0.7929	0.605	0.63	10
2.	P ₂ (1-2-6-9-10-12)	0.9147	0.822	0.556	0.558	6
3.	P ₃ (1-2-6-9-12)	0.91	0.7919	0.607	0.6367	11
4.	P ₄ (1-3-6-8-10-12)	0.9092	0.7788	0.636	0.66	13
5.	P ₅ (1-3-6-9-10-12)	0.9143	0.8044	0.584	0.5893	7
6.	P ₆ (1-3-6-9-12)	0.9094	0.7819	0.629	0.6557	12
7.	P ₇ (1-3-9-10-12)	0.921	0.8485	0.496	0.5174	2
8.	P ₈ (1-3-9-12)	0.919	0.8278	0.517	0.5304	4
9.	P ₉ (1-3-7-9-10-12)	0.9148	0.8248	0.544	0.5504	5
10.	P ₁₀ (1-3-7-9-12)	0.914	0.8018	0.589	0.6264	9
11.	P ₁₁ (1-3-7-12)	0.923	0.9194	0.354	0.402	1
12.	P ₁₂ (1-3-7-11-12)	0.9141	0.8031	0.587	0.6254	8
13.	P ₁₃ (1-4-7-9-10-12)	0.909	0.7386	0.716	0.7244	14
14.	P ₁₄ (1-4-7-9-12)	0.907	0.7179	0.757	0.7942	16
15.	P ₁₅ (1-4-7-12)	0.9199	0.8433	0.507	0.5248	3
16.	P ₁₆ (1-4-7-11-12)	0.9073	0.7305	0.732	0.7881	15

Table 5.1 Comparison Table

6. Conclusion

In this paper, a cosine similarity measure for the Pythagorean fuzzy set is proposed. An algorithm is also developed based on the newly proposed method which results in a suitable solution to recognize the shortest frequency path in a network. In future, the Pythagorean fuzzy set can be applied to medical diagnosis, machine learning systems, etc, with a different type of fuzzy measures.

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